

Improved Methodology for Calculating Interfacial Thermal Resistance and Uncertainty for Steady-State TIM Testers with Embedded Probes

Ronald J. Warzoha

Department of Mechanical Engineering
United States Naval Academy
Annapolis, Maryland 21402
Email: warzoha@usna.edu

Andrew N. Smith

Department of Mechanical Engineering
United States Naval Academy
Annapolis, Maryland 21402
Email: ansmith@usna.edu

Maurice Harris

Department of Mechanical Engineering
United States Naval Academy
Annapolis, Maryland 21402

Abstract—Efforts to miniaturize electronic components within the semiconductor industry continue to intensify stresses on the primary thermal pathways that are used for heat dissipation in electronics packaging equipment. This is particularly true for heat flow pathways that traverse interfaces. Consequently, an increasing priority for thermal engineers is to design materials that are capable of reducing the impedance to heat flow across device junctions. However, the equipment most often used to measure the resistance to heat flow across interfaces (ASTM D5470) is becoming increasingly insufficient for the characterization of next-generation thermal interface materials (TIMs), as evidenced by the wide variability in the reported results for current state-of-the-art TIMs. Through the use of statistical analyses, we show that one possible reason for these discrepancies is the method by which the temperature difference across the interface is calculated. Additionally, we find that there exists a lack of consideration for many potential sources of positional uncertainty that exist within the measurement system, including: 1) the thermal conductivity mismatch between the thermal probes, the heat meter bars and any interstitial filler material used to increase contact conductance between them, 2) drill drift during manufacturing, 3) the temperature and positional uncertainties of *each* probe along the length of the heat meter bars, 4) the tolerance associated with the location of each thermal probe's junction and 5) the number of thermal probes that are used to determine the temperature difference across the interface. We find that these factors result in an unavoidably large uncertainty in the position of the thermal probes, which produces a significant measurement uncertainty when R_T is on the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$ or lower, regardless of the temperature measurement accuracy that can be achieved with the probes. Using numerical simulations, we conduct a parametric study to determine the magnitude of these effects on positional uncertainty. Results suggest that the lowest positional uncertainty is achieved when the thermal probe is significantly less thermally conductive than its surrounding filler, and that drill drift and the uncertainty associated with the location of the actual thermal probe junction account for a significant increase in the overall uncertainty of the measurement. It is expected that these results will allow for the development of steady-state TIM characterization instruments with improved measurement resolutions and for greater consistency between the results of different groups that use thermal probe-based TIM testers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The thermal management of electronic devices represents one of only a few impediments to further reductions in the size of transistors in traditional integrated circuitry (IC) [1]. Until alternatives to conventional IC are fully developed [2], advances in transistor technologies will continue to rely heavily on our ability to dissipate increasing amounts of heat across ever-decreasing component footprints. However, advancements in heat sink and cold plate technologies are beginning to reach their fundamental cooling limits [1], while volume constraints for packaging continue to shrink. As a result, the interfaces that exist within the primary heat dissipation pathway often govern the temperatures of electronic components in many different devices. These issues have been well documented within the electronics packaging community [3], [4].

The thermal gradient that exists across an interface is primarily a function of the surface roughness and hardness of the two materials that are in contact with one another [4]. Even under significant pressure, air gaps form within the surface asperities across opposing interfaces (such as a heat spreader and a heat sink). Improvements in thermal transport across the junction between two such materials are usually achieved via the insertion of an interstitial material that is both thermally conductive and able to conform to micron-sized surface asperities [5]. Although transport physics dictate that some resistance to heat flow will always exist across a junction (even in the absence of surface asperities) [6], there still exists a significant opportunity to improve thermal conductance across electronics packaging interfaces [7]. In fact, this is now a major priority within the thermal community, as demonstrated by a recent DARPA initiative, the goal of which was to decrease the interfacial thermal resistance across common packaging component interfaces to $0.1 \text{ mm}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$ [8]. However, such a goal might be premature given the difficulty in obtaining consistent measurement results between lab groups [9].

One potential reason for these discrepancies could be the

Fig. 1: Heat Meter Bar Configuration

integrity (or lack thereof) associated with the current calculation methodology provided in ASTM D5470 [10], [11]. This method relies on the establishment of a linear thermal gradient that is imposed across the junction of two reference materials. The temperature difference across the interface is then extrapolated as a function of the applied heat flux (q'') along the length of the heat meter bars, the heat meter bar thermal properties and the measured thermal gradient along the length of the heat meter bars [12], as shown in Fig. 1. The ASTM method projects the temperature at each side of the interface (T_{c1} and T_{c2} in Eqn. 1) from a single point on each side of the heat meter bar [11].

$$\Delta T_{interface} = T_{c1} - T_{c2} \quad (1)$$

The temperature difference across the junction ($\Delta T_{interface}$) can then be used to calculate the total thermal resistance across the interface (R_T) based on Eqn. 2.

$$R_T = \frac{\Delta T_{interface}}{q''} \quad (2)$$

However, some groups suggest that this method may not yield accurate calculations of $\Delta T_{interface}$ at very low values of R_T [13]. This is primarily due to the difficulty associated with resolving $\Delta T_{interface}$ for high-performance TIMs. Currently, it is unknown to what extent the ASTM method is more or less accurate than a standard linear regression method when calculating the temperature at each side of the interface.

Also of significant concern is the integrity of the uncertainty calculations when high performance thermal interface materials (TIMs) are tested. For decades, most studies reported R_T without also reporting uncertainty [14]. It is possible that for early studies, R_T is large enough ($R_T \sim O(10^{-4} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K}/\text{W})$ [5]) that the uncertainty of the measurement is within common engineering standards ($U \sim O(10\%)$). However, recent advancements in the development of high performance TIMs [15]–[19] and the application of surface functional groups at interfaces [20]–[23] have reduced reported values of R_T by nearly two orders of magnitude. As noted in several recent studies [24], [25], however, the traditional methodology used to calculate R_T [11] may not be suitable for measurements

of this magnitude (particularly when utilizing thermal probes as the primary measurement instrument(s)), namely due to the inability to effectively resolve $\Delta T_{interface}$ for state-of-the-art TIMs). At sufficiently small values of $\Delta T_{interface}$, the uncertainty in the measurement of R_T is expected to increase significantly with increases in the temperature uncertainty of the thermal probes (U_T) and the location uncertainty of the temperature measurement (U_y).

In order to reduce the uncertainty in the measurement, Kempers et al. [14] use thermistors whose temperatures do not deviate by more than 0.001 K during a sufficiently long measurement period. This reduces contribution of U_T to the overall uncertainty in $\Delta T_{interface}$ by a significant margin. With a temperature measurement location uncertainty of only $20 \mu\text{m}$ (when considering the uncertainty in the hole diameter alone), the authors find that the maximum possible resolution for the device (with 10% engineering uncertainty) is $\sim 5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K}/\text{W}$. A similar approach has been taken in previous work [26].

Despite these promising results, there has been some debate about the true rigor of the methods used to calculate the uncertainty of $\Delta T_{interface}$ [13], [14], [26]. For instance, the authors of the present work are aware of only one study that attempts to determine the uncertainty of $\Delta T_{interface}$ as a function of the number of thermocouples that are embedded within each heat meter bar [26]. In their work, Kempers et al. [14] only consider the uncertainty in the location of each temperature measurement as it relates to the first and last thermal probe in each heat meter bar (Eqns. 10 and 11), which is unnecessarily conservative given that their calculation of the temperature at each interface relies on the slope of the thermal gradient along the heat meter bars generated by all of the embedded thermal probes.

Likewise, the authors are not aware of any work that makes clear the role of hole drift during drilling and the thermal conductivity mismatch between each thermal sensor and the material it's in contact with (i.e. thermal adhesive, heat meter bar, air, etc.) on $U_{\Delta T_{interface}}$. A thermal conductivity mismatch between the thermal probe and its surrounding material needs to be considered due to the alteration of the thermal gradient in close proximity to the location of the thermal probe's actual junction. These two factors alone could potentially result in an additional temperature measurement location uncertainty on the order of $100 \mu\text{m}$. The location of the temperature measurement along the junction itself can also affect this uncertainty. It is expected that the inclusion of these uncertainties will account for many of the discrepancies in the calculation of interfacial thermal resistance seen in the wider scientific literature.

In this work, we establish a calculation methodology for interfacial thermal resistance that includes an uncertainty analysis based on drill walk during thermal probe hole fabrication, a thermal conductivity mismatch between the thermal probe and its surrounding material and the number of thermal probes that are embedded within each heat meter bar (in addition to those uncertainties that are typically accounted for). One important

aspect of this work includes the use of COMSOL (v. 4.1) to conduct a parametric analysis such that practicing engineers can determine the influence of the thermal conductivity ratio between the thermal probe and its surrounding material on the uncertainty of each temperature measurement location. To do this, we conduct a parametric analysis that examines the effect of thermal probe thermal conductivity, the contacting material's thermal conductivity and the tolerance of the hole diameter. This is expected to allow for a significantly more accurate calculation of $U_{\Delta T_{interface}}$ in future work. These results can also serve as a critical design tool for the selection of thermal probes and the thermal paste to be used in the steady-state heat meter bar apparatus. Experiments are used in this work to examine the discrepancy between calculation methodologies for both the calculation of interfacial thermal resistance and its associated uncertainty. Finally, the minimum achievable interfacial thermal resistance using a steady-state technique is determined for the heat meter bars considered in this work.

II. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Calculation of Interfacial Thermal Resistance

The steady-state thermal interface material characterization technique is principally based on the ability to quantify a temperature gradient across the interface between two materials. When a heat flow, Q , is imposed across the junction, R_T can be calculated according to Eqn. 2. However, obtaining a value for $\Delta T_{interface}$ is not straightforward. In order to use Eqn. 2 (which is a modified form of Fourier's Law [27]), the heat must flow orthogonally with respect to the interface. As a consequence of this constraint, it becomes impractical to measure the temperatures at each side of the interface (even with advanced sensors [28], which tend to disrupt the orthogonality of heat flow across the interface). Because of this, the temperature at each side of the interface is usually extrapolated via the measurement of probe temperature vs. probe position along the length of two heat meter bars, as shown in Fig. 1.

In Fig. 1, L_{bars} represents the distance between the first and last thermal probes and δ represents the distance between two adjacent thermal probes. On the right hand side of Fig. 1 is the thermal resistance network that describes heat flow, Q , across the interface. Eqn. 1 can therefore be used to calculate $\Delta T_{interface}$, where T_{c1} and T_{c2} represent the temperature at the top and bottom of the junction, respectively.

Additionally, the total resistance across the interface can be separated into the individual components listed in Eqn. 3, where R_{TIM} is the resistance across any interstitial TIM that is inserted between the heat meter bars and R_{c1} and R_{c2} are the thermal contact resistances between the TIM and the upper and lower heat meter bars, respectively (a description of these resistances can be found in [4]).

$$R_T = R_{TIM} + R_{c1} + R_{c2} \quad (3)$$

In Eqn. 3, R_{c1} and R_{c2} are often considered to be equal to one another. As previously mentioned, it is difficult to resolve $\Delta T_{interface}$ using T_{c1} and T_{c2} experimentally due to restrictions in the proximity of the thermal sensors to the interface. Instead, it is convenient to use the thermal gradient in each of the heat meter bars to project a temperature at each side of the interface. One way to do this is to use the methodology described in ASTM D5470 [11]. According to ASTM D5470, Eqn. 4 can be used to calculate each of these temperatures (the top interface temperature (T_{c1}) is presented in Eqn. 4 as an example) .

$$T_{c1} = (T_{bottom} - \frac{\lambda}{(N-1) \cdot \delta} \cdot (T_{top} - T_{bottom})) \quad (4)$$

In Eqn. 4, T_{bottom} represents the temperature as read by a thermal probe in the location closest to the interface (at a distance λ from the interface), T_{top} represents the temperature within the heat meter bar at a distance $\lambda + L_{bars}$ from the interface and N is the number of thermal probes in a single heat meter bar. A similar procedure can be used to calculate the temperature at the bottom side of the interface (T_{c2}) [11], which yields $\Delta T_{interface}$ as described by Eqn. 1. In order to calculate R_T using $\Delta T_{interface}$, one must calculate a value for Q , which can be inferred from the slope of the thermal gradient along the length of each heat meter bar according to Eqn. 5. Here, k_{bars} represents the thermal conductivity of each heat meter bar and A_{bars} is the cross-sectional area of each heat meter bar. The slope is negative due to the direction of the heat flow pathway as illustrated in Fig. 1 (from top to bottom).

$$Q = -slope \cdot k_{bars} \cdot A_{bars} \quad (5)$$

One significant issue that emerges as a result of this methodology is that it assumes a perfectly linear temperature distribution within the heat meter bars. In theory, this should be the case so long as each heat meter bar does not experience any major heat loss and one-dimensional heat flow is established. However, even very well-insulated heat meter bars are subject to losses [14]. Additionally, the uncertainties in the hole positions and the temperatures of each individual probe are large enough that when R_T is sufficiently small (and thus $\Delta T_{interface}$ is sufficiently small), the temperatures T_{c1} and T_{c2} may actually overlap and/or result in a $-\Delta T_{interface}$, which will be demonstrated in the *Results* Section.

Alternatively, several groups utilize a slightly different approach to determine T_{c1} and T_{c2} [26]. In this alternative approach, the temperature at each side of the interface is determined by utilizing a linear regression that passes through each temperature measurement location. Though not explicitly stated in previous works, the slope and intercept of a linear regression ($t = A + B \cdot y$, where t is temperature and y is the position of each thermal probe along the length of the bar) are found according to Eqns. 6 and 7.

$$B = \frac{\sigma_{yt}}{\sigma_{yy}} \quad (6)$$

$$A = \bar{t} - B \cdot \bar{y} \quad (7)$$

In Eqns. 6 and 7 σ_{yy} and σ_{yt} are the covariance in xx and xt, respectively. These can be found according to Eqns. 8 and 9.

$$\sigma_{yy} = \sum (y - \bar{y})^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{yt} = \sum (y - \bar{y})(t - \bar{t}) \quad (9)$$

Thus, the linear regression methodology uses multiple temperature measurements along the length of the heat meter bar to project a temperature at the interface from the mean values of temperature and thermal probe position. While it is likely that multiple thermal probes will enhance the accuracy of the calculations associated with $\Delta T_{interface}$, the magnitude of this benefit has not been expressed within the literature (nor experimentally verified). As a result, it is not known to what degree the method used to calculate interfacial thermal resistance is useful at different magnitudes of R_T . Within practical limitations, we utilize a custom built experimental apparatus in order to distinguish between the calculations of R_T that are made using both the ASTM D5470 methodology and the linear regression analysis.

B. Uncertainty Analysis

The uncertainty associated with the measurement of interfacial thermal resistance using a steady-state, probe-based instrument is one of the more controversial aspects of TIM characterization. Here we examine traditional methods for assessing uncertainty and subsequently present a more robust method to compute the uncertainty of R_T . Using these results,

we report the expected maximum resolution for a steady-state thermal characterization apparatus.

Factors that have typically been incorporated within the uncertainty calculation of R_T include the uncertainty in the temperature of the thermal probes (U_T), the uncertainty in the location of the temperature measurement due to manufacturing limitations (U_y), the uncertainty in the thermal conductivity of the heat meter bars (U_k) and the uncertainty in the overlap area between reference bars (U_A , or the alignment of the reference bars). Other factors, such as thermal probe calibration uncertainty, heat loss uncertainty and the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of the heat meter bars (particularly for OFHC copper), have negligible influence on the uncertainty of such measurements [14].

The uncertainty in the position of the temperature measurement is often cited as the dominant uncertainty in the calculation of R_T [14]. Traditionally, temperature measurement location uncertainty is computed according to the tolerance of the hole diameter used to house each thermal probe. One concern is that several groups have only used the first and last temperature measurement locations in each heat meter bar to determine the uncertainty, despite using multiple probes to calculate $\Delta T_{interface}$. The resulting displacement in the temperature at a single interface $\Delta T \delta_n$ is shown in Fig. 2 (where the blue holes represent the expected placement and the red holes represent the actual placement), which is significantly greater than the displacement in temperature as calculated when using all of the data points to calculate this uncertainty. The temperature and positional uncertainties that result from the use of the two endpoints that project a temperature to the interface are presented in Eqns. 10 and 11.

Fig. 2: U_{hp} Uncertainty Calculation Methodology

$$U_{\Delta T_{interface}} = \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot U_y}{k_{mb} \cdot R \cdot A \cdot \Delta T} \quad (10)$$

$$U_y = \frac{U_T}{\sqrt{2} \cdot m_{mb}} \quad (11)$$

In Eqn. 10, k_{mb} is the thermal conductivity of the heat meter bar material. In Eqn. 11, m_{mb} is the slope of the thermal gradient through an individual heat meter bar. Alternatively, the uncertainty associated with the measurement of temperature by the thermal sensors can be coupled with the uncertainty in the hole position and the number of thermocouples in each heat meter bar to produce a total uncertainty in the measurement of the temperature difference across the interface ($2 \cdot \Delta T \cdot \delta_n / (\Delta T_{interface})$) in Fig. 2). Rather than using two individual data points to calculate this uncertainty, we propose the use of Eqns. 12, 13 and 14.

$$U_{\Delta T} = \left(U_T^2 + \left(\frac{dT}{dy} \cdot U_y \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sum y^2}{N \cdot \sum (y - \bar{y})^2}} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$U_s = \left(U_T^2 + \left(\frac{dT}{dy} \cdot U_y \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{N \cdot \sum (y - \bar{y})^2}} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$U_{R_T} = \left(\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial s} \right)^2 \cdot U_s^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial \Delta T} \right)^2 \cdot U_{\Delta T}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial k_{bars}} \right)^2 \cdot U_{k_{bars}}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (14)$$

In Eqns. 12, 13 and 14, U_T is the uncertainty in the temperature measurement at each probe location, U_y is the uncertainty in the location of the temperature measurement, $U_{\bar{y}}$ is the uncertainty in the center point of the heat meter bars, x is the distance from the uppermost point of the top heat meter bar to each thermal probe location, \bar{y} is the midpoint of each heat meter bar and N is the number of thermal probes used in each heat meter bar. $U_{\Delta T}$ in Eqn. 12 is the uncertainty in the calculated temperature difference across the interface. U_s in Eqn. 13 is the uncertainty in the slope of the thermal gradient due to heat loss. Finally, U_{R_T} is the total uncertainty of the measurement, which includes the uncertainty of the thermal conductivity of the bars. According to this set of equations, the uncertainty varies as $\sim 1/\sqrt{N}$. As a result, the uncertainty in the measurement of the temperature at the interface decreases as the number of thermal probes in each heat meter bar increases.

One additional concern with uncertainty analyses presented within the wider literature is that U_y is typically based only on the uncertainty in the diameter of the hole that houses the thermal probe. For instance, Kempers et. al [14] measured the diameter of their drilled holes for 0.38 mm diameter,

high precision thermistors using opticomechanical instrumentation and found the average hole diameter to be 0.42 mm, resulting in a $\pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ uncertainty in the location of their thermistors. However, their analysis does not consider the uncertainty of the location of the thermal sensor within its own sheating/soldered bead, which could itself range between 20 μm and 100 μm , nor does it account for the possibility of drift during drilling. Additionally, the thermal conductivity mismatch between the probe and adhesive used to hold it in place and/or between the probe and the heat meter bar will offset the location of the temperature measurement. As will be shown in the *Results* section, this can lead to significantly higher measurement uncertainties (particularly for high performance TIMs).

C. Experimental Verification

In order to verify the claims made in this work, a steady-state device is used to measure R_T across two different types of interfaces, each with varying magnitudes of expected thermal resistance. The foundation for the experimental apparatus used in this work is typical of a conventional heat meter bar apparatus found in many other scientific laboratories. However, some modifications were made to isolate the effects of temperature and positional uncertainty for the thermal probes on the overall uncertainty of its measurements. For instance,

Fig. 3: Heat Meter Bar Apparatus

Fig. 4: Surface Finish for Heat Meter Bar Interfaces

efforts were made to reduce the uncertainty in alignment using a 6-axis micrometer stage at the top of the apparatus as well as a triangular pattern of load cells at the bottom of the apparatus. Alignment is achieved via load balance; in this case, the total load is distributed atop three button-type load cells that are arranged in a circular pattern with angular separation distances of 120° . Once the load cells read to within 1 % of each other, the heat meter bars are considered to be aligned with one another *and* perpendicular with respect to the bottom plate of the apparatus. Additionally, the entire apparatus is placed within a vacuum chamber in order to mitigate the effects of convective heat loss on the temperature distribution within the heat meter bars. These modifications are shown in Fig. 3. The heat meter bar apparatus contains two reference bars fabricated with Oxygen-free High Conductivity (OFHC) Copper ($k_{OFHC} = 400 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ [18]). A total of five N-type thermocouples (diameter = $8\cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}$) are inserted into each of the top and bottom heat meter bars and separated by a distance $\delta = 0.02 \text{ m}$. The heat meter bars themselves have $22.5 \text{ mm} \times 22.5 \text{ mm}$ cross sections and can be aligned via a 6-axis mechanical stage at the top of the instrument.

The heat meter bar surface finish is shown in Fig. 4. A ball milling process was used to polish the surface to an average surface roughness of $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ (according to statistical analyses obtained with the use of the optical profilometer). A roughness profile of the z-direction centerline is provided to the right of the surface profile.

Heat is applied at the top of the upper heat meter bar for a number of reasons. First, it ensures that convection within the TIM or the surface asperities at the mating interfaces does not contribute significantly to the thermal gradient across the junction, which is particularly important when characterizing TIMs that are porous or that do not completely eliminate air gaps between surface asperities [16]. The heat flow is applied using DC cartridge heaters and is temperature limited to match the constraints of practical electronic systems ($T_{heaters} = 100^\circ\text{C}$). To help prevent heat loss from the upper heat meter bar to the instrumentation above it, a guard heater is used

and temperature matched to the top-most part of the upper heat meter bar via a temperature controller. Because R_T is known to be a strong function of pressure [4], a pneumatic piston is used to apply pressure at the interface. To prevent heat loss from the heat meter bars to the surrounding environment, the system is insulated using either 0.1 m thick fibrous ceramic insulation (for interstitial materials that do not completely conform to the surface asperities at each copper interface) or a custom vacuum chamber capable of achieving a pressure of $P \sim 1\cdot 10^{-4} \text{ Pa}$ (for interstitial materials that completely conform to the surface asperities at each copper interface). Finally, a cold plate ($T_{cp} = 10^\circ\text{C}$) is used to establish a linear thermal gradient from the top of the upper heat meter bar to the bottom of the lower heat meter bar, where the minimum temperature is limited by condensation along the length of the bottom heat meter bar. Using this apparatus, seven different materials are tested and their uncertainties quantified according to the methodologies provided in the subsequent subsection.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we characterize the interfacial thermal resistance across two different junctions using a conventional steady-state heat meter bar apparatus with embedded thermocouples. The interfaces we test include: 1) copper-copper and 2) copper-indium. The indium is a ‘soft metal’ that is expected to produce an interfacial thermal resistance between 1 and $10 \text{ mm}^2\cdot\text{K/W}$ when embedded between copper heat meter bars with smooth surfaces (R_a , average surface roughness, $< 10 \mu\text{m}$ [25]). It is important to note that this work is not meant to uncover thermal transport properties across state-of-the-art thermal interface material junctions; rather, its intention is to thoughtfully examine the mechanisms that contribute to the uncertainty in the calculation of the temperature difference across the interface.

A. Uncertainty Analysis

In this work, we consider the uncertainty in the diameter of the hole to be on the order of $25 \mu\text{m}$ based on optical profilometry measurements of the hole diameter. Additionally,

Fig. 5: Temperature contours for 2D heat flow around the thermal probe hole when the probe thermal conductivity is 100 times less than the heat meter bar; and the filler thermal compound thermal conductivity is 10 times less than the probe.

we use a drill walk of approximately 1.5 mm per meter of drilled depth, which results in an additional $11.25 \mu\text{m}$ of positional uncertainty [29].

In order to determine the effect of the thermal conductivity ratio between the thermal probe and the surrounding material, a parametric analysis was conducted with the aid of numerical simulations. The thermal conductivity mismatch between the thermal probe, heat meter bar and the thermal compound used to fill the hole was explored using a simple COMSOL model. The computational domain was selected to be 10 times the diameter of the hole. The tolerance between the hole and the probe diameter was assumed to be 0.5% of the hole diameter. As a conservative measure, the probe was located at the maximum vertical position within the hole. Conductivity ratios were varied for both the heat meter bar to probe, and the probe to the filler thermal compound. The upper boundary was set to 400 K while the lower boundary was set to 300 K. As seen in Fig. 5, the temperature at the center of the probe is higher than 350K. This temperature difference was then used to estimate the shift in position using the imposed temperature gradient. In the limit where the fill is insulating, the positional uncertainty will be shifted by more than the hole diameter due to the heat flow around the hole.

In order to generalize these findings, we generated a non-dimensionalized chart via parametric analysis for use by others to determine the influence of thermal conductivity mismatch on the uncertainty of the location of their thermal probes (and ultimately on their total uncertainty), as shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

Figure 6 shows that the positional uncertainty is directly related to the tolerance when there is no mismatch ($k_{probe}/k_{bar}=1$ and $k_{probe}/k_{filler}=1$, where k_{probe} is the thermal conductivity of the probe and k_{fill} is the thermal conductivity of the filler material). In practice, the probe thermal conductivity is

generally less than heat meter bar thermal conductivity. Figure 6 shows that the uncertainty increases by a factor of 2 when the probe thermal conductivity is 10 times less than the heat meter bar, which is the result of heat flow around the lower conductivity regions. Figure 6 also shows that the conductivity of the filler has a very strong influence and (ideally) the thermal conductivity of the filler should be greater than the probe thermal conductivity. As the filler thermal conductivity goes to infinity, the probe location within the hole becomes immaterial. These results can now be used to more precisely calculate the uncertainty for the measurement of interfacial thermal resistance across steady-state heat meter bars with embedded probes.

Figure 7 suggests that lower values of k_{probe}/k_{fill} correspond to lower positional uncertainties, which means that the probe's thermal conductivity should generally be lower than the filler material's. Additionally, this work suggests that an increase in the percentage of the hole that is occupied by the filler results in an increase in positional uncertainty when $k_{probe} < k_{fill}$ and a decrease in positional uncertainty when $k_{probe} > k_{fill}$.

As an example of the impact that these additional uncertainties have on the overall uncertainty of a measurement made by a steady-state, probe-based apparatus, the uncertainty for this work is broken down into its constituent parts in Table I. Also on this table are the additional uncertainty contributions studied in this work added to the work by Kempers et al. [14] in order to better reflect the true uncertainty of their measurement.

In Table I, the drill drift was assumed to be 1.5 mm per meter of drilled heat meter bar [29], while the probe position uncertainty due to thermal conductivity mismatch between the heat meter bars and/or probes is taken directly from Fig. 6. The value of $k_{mismatch}$ in Table I represents the thermal conductivity ratio between the thermal probes and the filler material. The uncertainty in probe junction location is estimated to be the lower limit of the tolerance of the thermal junction location within its own sheathing, bead, or along the metal junction itself, and the temperature uncertainty is taken from the standard deviation in the measurement of temperature at each thermal probe location when operating at steady state. The resulting uncertainty in the position of temperature measurements along the length of the heat meter bars is $\sim 142 \mu\text{m}$ for the present study and $\sim 88 \mu\text{m}$ for the study conducted by Kempers et al. [14], which is over 4 times larger than that estimated within the original work.

Hypothetically, if five thermal probes with uncertainties of 0.001 K are used in each heat meter bar (where bar length is equal to $\sim 100 \text{ mm}$) and the uncertainty in the position of the thermal probes is nearly five times greater at a thermal interface resistance of $1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$ for calculations that include a temperature measurement location uncertainty of $100 \mu\text{m}$ (39% uncertainty versus 8% uncertainty when only the hole diameter uncertainty is considered in the calculation of temperature measurement location uncertainty). With less accurate thermal probes (i.e. $U_T = 0.1$), the uncertainty

Study	Uncertainty Value				
	Hole Diameter (μm)	Drill Drift (μm)	$k_{mismatch}$	Probe Junction Location (μm)	Temperature (K)
<i>Present Study</i>	25	17	80	20	0.1
<i>Kempers et al. [14]</i>	25	30	13	20	0.001

TABLE I: Uncertainty Analysis for Present Study and Kempers et al. [14]

increases to well over 100% when R_T is on the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K}/\text{W}$. As a result, it is unlikely that the conventional, probe-based ASTM methodology is suitable for measuring next-generation thermal interface materials.

B. Comparison of ASTM Methodology with Linear Regression Analysis

The current standard used to calculate the thermal resistance across an interface with a steady-state heat meter bar apparatus is ASTM D5470 [11]. This standard uses Eqns. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 in order to calculate R_T . The principal disadvantage of this standard is that it uses a single temperature measurement and location to project the temperature at each interface (see Eqn. 4). Consequently, significant error in this projection can occur with only a small measurement uncertainty in either the thermocouple position or its temperature measurement.

According to Eqn. ??, it can be substantially more accurate to use as many thermocouples as possible to project the temperature at each interface by evaluating the slope of a linear regression through the ensuing temperature/position distribution on each heat meter bar (assuming that heat flow is strictly one-dimensional and that the thermocouples are evenly spaced). A few groups have already used this method

to calculate both the thermal resistance across the interface and the uncertainty in this calculation [21], [26], while others have either used this method to calculate the temperature difference across the interface, but not the uncertainty in their calculation of $\Delta T_{interface}$ [14], [30] or have favored the ASTM methodology altogether [31]–[34]. While it is likely that the linear regression methodology used in [21], [26], [30] is likely to be more accurate, the relative uncertainty for each methodology at different values of R_c has not been compared. Thus, one goal of this work is to examine the effect of calculation methodology on measurement uncertainty for different measured values of R_T .

The calculated interfacial thermal resistance (R_T) for each junction type used in this work is shown in Fig. 8. In this figure, both the ASTM standard and the linear regression method are used to calculate R_T .

Although not immediately clear in Fig. 8, the interfacial thermal resistances calculated for the copper-copper and copper-indium interfaces are separated by nearly two orders of magnitude. It should be noted that the thickness of the indium foil was maintained at ~ 4 mil for the duration of the test in accordance with the tolerances in the co-author's previous work [13]. For the copper-copper interface, the calculated

Fig. 6: Influence of the thermal conductivity mismatch between the heat meter bar and the probe (k_{probe}/k_{bar}) and between the probe and the filler thermal compound (k_{probe}/k_{filler}) on the positional uncertainty U_y for the thermal probe for a monolithic probe.

Fig. 7: Influence of the thermal conductivity mismatch between the filler and the probe (k_{probe}/k_{fill}) as a function of gap fill ratio $(r_{hole} - r_{probe}) / r_{hole}$.

result for the interfacial thermal resistance differed by about 15%, each with predicted uncertainties of about 10%. Importantly, the calculation for the interfacial thermal resistance remained at the same order of magnitude, indicating that the ASTM method is sufficient for calculating the interfacial thermal resistance across interfaces with $R_c = 1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$. However, a closer examination of R_T as calculated for the indium foil reveals that the results and uncertainties for the two calculation methodologies diverge significantly at just a one order of magnitude reduction in R_T , as shown in Fig. 9.

In Fig. 9, the deviation between the results of the interfacial thermal resistance as calculated using the ASTM methodology vs. the linear regression methodology is significant (nearly an order of magnitude different). For $R_T \sim 2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$, the uncertainty is almost as high as 500% for very large pressures (and extends into a non-positive measurement result), indicating that the ASTM methodology is not suitable for use with measurements of R_T at this order of magnitude.

Though the calculation of R_T is different for the linear regression method than the ASTM methodology, the resulting uncertainty for a value of R_T on the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$ is still 100% (it should be noted that Eqn. 11 is used to calculate the uncertainty for the ASTM methodology while Eqns. 12-14 are used to calculate the uncertainty for the linear regression methodology). While this does indicate that the linear regression methodology is likely sufficient to calculate R_T on the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$, the use of thermal probes is likely to limit the resolution of steady-state heat meter bar testers to $1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$ due to the large uncertainty in the location of the temperature measurements along the length of the heat meter bars.

Fig. 8: Interfacial Thermal Resistance Across Copper-Copper and Copper-Indium Interfaces as Calculated with the ASTM Methodology and the Linear Regression Methodology

IV. CONCLUSION

It was shown that the ASTM methodology was sufficient to resolve the interfacial resistance with an uncertainty of less than 10% when measuring interfaces with a resistance greater than $1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$. However, utilizing a more thorough linear regression analysis to determine both the slope and the temperature at the interface significantly reduced the uncertainty of the derived quantity, R_T , for higher performance interfaces on the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$. The ASTM methodology only utilizes two probes to determine the slope and projects the interfacial temperature from a single point. Increasing the number of thermal probes reduces the uncertainty

Fig. 9: Interfacial Thermal Resistance Across Copper-Indium Interface as Calculated with the ASTM Methodology and the Linear Regression Methodology

of the measured slope and ultimately the uncertainty in the projected temperature at the interface. This was shown through a rigorous uncertainty analysis that took into account the uncertainty in the thermal probe, U_T , and the probe position, U_y . Traditionally, the uncertainty of the probe position has been taken to be on the order of the clearance between the hole diameter and the diameter of the thermal probe. It was shown that the influence of centerline drift during drilling, and the mismatch between the thermal conductivity of the probe, thermal compound and the heat meter bar significantly increase the position uncertainty. Using a low conductivity probe with a high thermal conductivity thermal compound decreases the probe positional uncertainty. Experimental results for a standard TIM tester are presented for a low performance Cu-Cu interface and a high performance interface using indium foil. The improved methodology significantly reduced the uncertainty of the measure R_T values for the high performance interface. Finally, the uncertainty analysis presented in this paper will allow researchers to reliably estimate the maximum resolution of conventional ASTM testers, which should reduce the amount of discrepancy seen within the literature.

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